

A Study of Correlation of Complexity of Surgery with Post-Operative Complications using Clavien-Dindo Score

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Abstract:

Aim: This study aimed to analyze the correlation of Clavien-Dindo classification for complications in post-operative period with the complexity of surgeries.

Materials and Methods: This prospective, observational study was conducted on 200 patients undergoing elective and emergency surgery after fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The operations were sorted according to the complexity ranking according to British United Provident Association (BUPA) scores. Parameters like operative procedure, length of post-operative period, postoperative complications and management were recorded and postsurgical complications were classified based on Clavien-Dindo classification.

Result: In this study, out of the 200 included patients, 127 patients (63.5%) were male, 73 patients (36.5%) were female. The study found that Grade 2 complication was more common in minor surgery (33.5%), followed by Grade 1 (24.5%). Grade-I complications were more common in intermediate surgery (21.6%) and Major surgery (II) (83.3%). Major plus surgery (43.2%) had the most common Grade-II complications (43.2%), followed by Grade-IIIb (17.2%). In elective surgery (41.2%), Grade-II complications were higher (41.2%), while Grade-IIIb complications were more common in emergency surgery (requiring surgical, endoscopic, or radiological intervention under general anesthesia), which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). 6.5% of patients developed disability and the majority were in the major surgery group.

Conclusion: The Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications can be used in both elective and emergency surgery patients. BUPA Score is a simple and easier method to classify complexity of surgery and we can easily correlate the complexity of surgery and complications with the Clavien Dindo Classification.

Keywords: Complexity of surgery, post-operative complications, Clavien-Dindo Score, Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications.

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Introduction

Surgical intervention is a critical component of modern medicine, often providing life-saving solutions to various health conditions. However, the complexity of surgical procedures can lead to a range of postoperative complications, which significantly impact patient outcomes and healthcare costs. The Clavien-Dindo Classification (CDC) has emerged as a standardized tool for assessing these complications, categorizing them based on the severity and the therapeutic interventions required for resolution. Clavien et al. in 1992, proposed a complication scoring system categorizing complications depending on the required treatment [1]. It was revised in 2004 and

has since been referred to as the Clavien-Dindo Classification (CDC). This classification system has gained widespread acceptance due to its simplicity and reproducibility across diverse surgical disciplines [2-7]. The correlation between the complexity of surgical procedures and the incidence of postoperative complications is an area of increasing interest in surgical research. Previous studies have demonstrated that more complex surgeries are associated with higher complication rates, which in turn can extend hospital stays and increase healthcare costs [5, 8]. Understanding this relationship is crucial for improving surgical practices and patient care, as it allows for better

risk stratification and resource allocation. Moreover, the Clavien-Dindo score not only provides a framework for documenting complications but also facilitates the comparison of surgical outcomes across different institutions and practices [2, 7]. By analyzing the correlation between surgical complexity and postoperative complications using the Clavien-Dindo score, this study aims to identify patterns that can inform clinical decision-making and enhance patient safety. The findings from this research could contribute to establishing benchmarks for surgical quality and ultimately improve patient outcomes in various surgical fields.

The Clavien-Dindo classification, under the name of "T92 score," provided the benefits of comparing outcomes over time within the same institution, comparing different institutions, comparing conservative and surgical treatments, and standardizing the documentation of operations and related complications, all of which facilitated meta-analyses. Consequently, prognostic ratings could be used. Clavien and Dindo discarded length of stay (LOS) in this new updated version in 2004, since it differed too strongly between hospitals due to internal rules governing when to discharge a patient. The Clavien-Dindo classification was also used in several other studies [9-13] which proved it an easy, comparable and standard tool in quality management. This present study aimed to analyze the correlation of Clavien-Dindo classification for complications in post-operative period with the complexity of surgeries in the general surgery ward of a tertiary care referral centre.

Materials & Method

This prospective, observational study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Kalaburagi with due permission from the institutional ethical committee and review board and written informed patient consent.

Study duration: October 2023 to October 2024 or predefined sample size is achieved, whichever is earlier.

Sample size: Study was conducted on 200 patients undergoing elective and emergency surgery after informed and written consent.

Inclusion Criteria

- Elective and emergency surgery
- All negative incident occurring in a patient after surgery irrespective whether there was or was not a clear correlation with former surgical intervention
- Consenting for the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Complication developed after discharge

- Initially operated at another institute or any other department
- Pregnant females
- Those not consenting to the study

Methodology

After the ethical committee granted approval for this study, patients were selected according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria who will be admitted in the general surgery ward. During the study period 200 patients who had undergone surgery and developed complications after the surgery were selected. The selected patients for study were evaluated by detailed clinical history, comorbid conditions were given importance and thorough clinical examination were done. Routine investigations and specific investigations like x-ray, USG and CT scan were done depending upon the provisional diagnosis and requirement. The operations were sorted according to the complexity ranking according to British United Provident Association (BUPA) scores.

Parameters like operative procedure, length of post-operative period, postoperative complications and management were recorded and postsurgical complications were classified based on Clavien-Dindo classification. The highest grade of postoperative complications was chosen if the patient developed multiple complications.

Observation & Results

In this study, out of the 200 included patients, 127 patients (63.5%) were male, 73 patients (36.5%) were female. In this study population, 17 patients (8.5%) belonged to the age group <20 years, 32 patients (16%) in the age group of 21 to 30 years, 39 patients (19.5%) in the age group of 31 to 40 years, and 41 to 50 years, 35 patients (17.5%) in the age group of 51 to 60 years and 38 patients (19%) in the age group of more than 60 years. Majority (56.5%) of the patients were in the age group of 31 to 60 years.

Majority (39.37%) of the male patients were in the age group of >50 years and the majority (42.47%) of female patients in the age group 31-50 years of age. 109 patients (54.5%) were subjected to elective surgeries and 91 patients (45.5%) underwent emergency surgeries.

All the patients who developed complications were classified according to the BUPA Score and the majority of the patients fall under the major or major plus surgeries group.

There were 6 patients (3%) who underwent minor, 37 (18.5%) underwent Intermediate, 57 (28.5%) underwent Major, 81 (40.5%) underwent Major Plus and 19 (9.5%) patients underwent Complex major surgeries out of the 200 patients who developed complications.

In the study population (n = 200), 49 patients (24.5%) developed Grade-I complication, 67 patients (33.5%) developed Grade-II complications, 8 patients (4%) developed Grade-IIIa complications, 36 patients (18%) developed Grade-IIIb complications, 8 patients (4%) developed Grade-IVa, 8 patients (4%) developed Grade-IVb complications and 24 patients (12%) developed Grade-V complications.

Table 1 shows 6 patients who underwent minor surgeries, 5 patients (83.3%, 2.5% of all) developed Grade-I complication, 1 patients (16.6%, 0.5% of all) developed Grade-II complications and none of them developed and complications of Grade-III or higher.

Out of 37 patients who underwent intermediate surgeries, 17 patients (45.9%, 8.5% of all) developed Grade-I complication, 8 patients (21.6%, 4% of all) developed Grade-II complications, 2 patients (5.4%, 1% of all) developed Grade-IIIa complications, 8 patients (21.6%, 4% of all) developed Grade-IIIb complications, 1(2.7%, 0.5% of all) patient developed Grade-IVb, 1(2.7%, 0.5% of all) patient developed Grade-V complication and none of the patient developed Grade-IVa complications.

57 patients who underwent Major surgeries the rate of different complications grades were

14patients (28.5%, 7% of all) developed Grade-I complication, 18 patients (31.5%, 9% of all)

developed Grade-II complications, 3 patients (5.2%, 1.5% of all) developed Grade-IIIa complications, 12 patients (21.05%, 6% of all) developed Grade-IIIb complications, 2 patients (3.5%, 1% of all) developed Grade-IVa complications, 3 patients (5.2%, 1.5% of all) developed Grade-IVb and 5 patients (8.7%, 2.5% of all) developed Grade-V complication

Out of 81 patients who underwent Major Plus surgeries, 12 patients (23.5%, 6% of all) developed Grade-I complication, 35 patients (43.2%,9% of all) developed Grade-II complications, 3 patients (3.7%, 1.5% of all) developed Grade-IIIa complications, 14 patients (17.2%, 7% of all) developed Grade-IIIb complications, 4 patients(4.9%, 2% of all) developed Grade-IVa complications, 3 patients (3.7%,1.5% of all)developed Grade-IVb and 10 patients (12.3%, 5%of all) developed Grade-V complication.

19 patients had undergone Complex Major surgeries, in which 1 patients (5.2%, 0.5% of all) developed Grade-I complication, 5 patients (26.3%, 4.5% of all) developed Grade-II complications, 2 patients (10.5%, 1% of all) developed Grade- IIIb complications, 2 patients (10.5%, 1% of all) developed Grade-IVa complications, 1 patients (5.2%, 0.5% of all) developed Grade-IVb and 8 patients (44.4%, 4% of all) developed Grade-V complication and none of the patients developed complication of Grade-IIIa.

Table 1: Correlation between Clavien-Dindo Score and BUPA Score.

Clavien-Dindo score	Minor	Intermediate	Major	Major Plus	Complex Major	p Value
Grade-I	5	17	14	12	1	0.0007
Grade-II	1	8	18	35	5	
Grade-IIIa	0	2	3	3	0	
Grade-IIIb	0	8	12	14	2	
Grade-IVa	0	0	2	4	2	
Grade-IVb	0	1	3	3	1	
Grade-V	0	1	5	10	8	

Table 2 shows that in 109 patients who had undergone elective surgeries the rate of complications is: Grade-I 33%, Grade-II 41.2%, Grade-IIIa 3.6%, Grade-IIIb 9.17%, Grade-IVa 2.7%, Grade-IVb 2.7% and Grade-V 7.3%. Out of 91 patients who had undergone emergency surgeries Grade-I complications developed in 14.2%, Grade-II in 24.1%, Grade-IIIa 4.3%, Grade-IIIb 28.5%, Grade-IVa 5.4%, Grade-IVb 5.4%, Grade-V 17.5%.

Table 2: Correlation between Clavien-Dindo Score and Type of Surgery.

Clavien-Dindo Score	Elective	Emergency	p Value
Grade-I	36	13	0.00009
Grade-II	45	22	
Grade-IIIa	4	4	
Grade-IIIb	10	26	
Grade-IVa	3	5	
Grade-IVb	3	5	
Grade-V	8	16	

13 patients (6.5%) in the study group developed disability in which 12 patients had Major surgery

and 1 patient had Major Plus surgery. 187 patients (93.5%) didn't show any disability. In the study

population, 24 patients (12%) had Grade-V complications i.e. death. 5 patients (8.7%, 2.5% of all) developed Grade-V complication who had undergone Major Surgery, 10 patients (12.3%, 5% of all) developed Grade-V complication in Major plus surgery and 8 patients (44.4%, 4% of all) developed Grade-V complication in Complex Major surgery. Among 109 patients who had undergone elective Surgery 7.3% mortality rate was present while among 91 patients after emergency surgery the mortality rate was 17.5%.

Discussion

This prospective study involved 200 patients admitted for any type of general surgical procedure including both elective as well as emergency

Table 3: Comparison of gender in present study with previous studies.

	Present study	Bollinger et al [5]	Mentula et al [14]
Male	63.5%	53.7%	48%
Female	36.5%	46.3%	52%

In this group, the majority of the male patients were in the age group of > 50 years and female patients in the age group of 31-50 years. In a study by Mentula et al. [14] the median age of patients was 50 years which is similar. Park et al. [15] conducted a study over general surgery patients in which the mean age was 64.2 ± 13.9 years. Complexity of surgery was graded according to BUPA Score and majority fall under the Major plus (40.5%) group and most commonly performed surgeries in that group were exploratory laparotomy with stoma for intestinal obstruction or perforation peritonitis and then major group (28.5%) in which frequently done procedures were laparoscopic cholecystectomy, open appendectomy and limb amputations.

In our study, the complications belonged more frequently to Grades-I and II, constituting about two-thirds of the patients with complications requiring only pharmacological treatment, whereas one-third of the patients required management in the ICU or interventional treatment. In our study population (n = 200), 116 patients developed complications during their postoperative period among which 116 patients (58%) developed low grade complications, 60 patients (30%) developed high grade complications. Among low grades, Grade-II is most common.

In their study, M. Bollinger et al. [5] comprised 517 patients with 817 hospitalizations, 463 of whom had undergone surgery. Of the 12.5% who experienced problems, he discovered that 19% were classified as Grade I, 20.7% as Grade II, 13.8% as Grade IIIa, 27.6% as Grade IIIb, 8.6% as Grade IVa, and 10.3% as Grade V. During the investigation, there were no Grade-IVb complications. Hospital stays were noticeably longer for those who had more complicated surgeries or who scored higher. Park et al [15]

surgery in different age groups of patients with different comorbid conditions. Post-operative complications were studied in each of these patients and graded according to Clavien–Dindo classification.

In this classification, Grades-I and II can be treated with drugs, blood transfusions, physiotherapy and nutrition, while Grades- III and IV require surgical, endoscopic or radiologic intervention, and intermediate care or ICU management and Grade-V assigned to patient who died in postoperative period.

This grading system was objective and simple because the data recorded in our database were easily converted into this new classification.

conducted study on 240 patients in general surgery department and Clavien Dindo classification Grades-I, II, III, IV, and IV, there were 113 (47.08%), 63 (26.25%), 42 (17.50%), 15 (6.25%), 3 (1.25%), and 4 (1.67%) patients, respectively. Regarding most commonly occurring complications, in Grade-I, post-operative nausea, vomiting and pain are most commonly encountered problems. In Grade-II, two leading complications were surgical site infection and hemorrhage requiring blood transfusion. The grades 3 to 5 complication rate was within the range described in the literature, and the rate of Grades-I and II complications was substantially higher. Patients with Grade-I and those without problems are comparable because Grade-I only included wound infections that appeared at the patient's bedside and did not involve any specific pharmaceutical treatment.

Organ dysfunctions that were previously existing prior to surgery were not considered problems in our study; that is, the patient's condition was unaffected by the organ dysfunctions. However, a complication was categorized as Grade-IV if the patient experienced additional postoperative difficulties that likely resulted in persistent organ dysfunctions or worsening of organ dysfunctions. Additionally, any organ failure that progressed to death was categorized as a Grade-V consequence. Because surgical trauma can cause postoperative organ dysfunctions any new organ failure occurring after surgery is a deviation from ideal postoperative course and should be classified as a complication according to the Clavien-Dindo classification.

16 patients (8%) developed organ dysfunction in which 8 patients developed single organ dysfunction and 8 patients developed multi organ dysfunction. Bollinger et al [5] conducted a study

in which organ dysfunction complications were seen in 8.6% patients which is comparable but they have recorded single organ dysfunction in all patients. In Emergency surgery, Grade-IIIb complications were the common (28.5%) Mentula et al [14] conducted study and check the applicability of Clavien-Dindo Score in emergency surgery and found that Grade-III and Grade-II complications are equally common and Grade-IIIb complication were found in 15.6% patients. Re-operation chances are more after emergency surgery, Oscar A. Guevara et al. [16] conducted a study to find out whether emergency surgery is a risk factor for unplanned reoperation or not and in his study, there was 5.9% cumulative incidence of unplanned reoperation. Patients operated on in emergency conditions had a 1.79 crude relative risk (RR) of reoperation.

BUPA Score and Clavien-Dindo Score relation were compared in this study and this is the first ever study which has compared these two parameters. It was found that in the minor surgery group 83.3% developed Grade-I and remaining developed Grade-II complications and none of the patients developed any higher grade of complications.

In the intermediate surgery group 45.9% developed Grade-I complication followed by Grade-II and Grade-IIIb while the percentage of developing other higher grades of complications were very low. Those who have undergone Major surgery the rate of Grade-II complications was higher (31.5%) followed by Grade-I (28.5%) and Grade-III (26.25%) and other higher-grade complications were seen more than the minor and intermediate surgery group.

In the major plus surgery group Grade-II complications occurred more frequently (43.2%) followed by Grade-I (23.5%) and Grade-III (20.9%). The occurrence of complications Grade-III in major plus surgery group were similar to major surgery group but the rate of Grade-V complication was seen higher in Major plus group (12.3%) than Major surgery (8.7%).

The patients who underwent Complex Major Surgery Grade-V complications were the most frequent (44.4%). In this group patients developed Grade-IV and Grade-V significantly higher than any other group.

Thus, it can be inferred from our study that the minor and intermediate group developed a low grade of complications while the Major and Major plus group developed Grade-II more frequently but other higher grades of complications are much higher than the minor and intermediate group. Complex major surgery develops higher grade of complications than any other group. The above study shows that as the complexity increases the grade of complications gets higher. In our study disability was seen in 6.5% of the patients and

mostly in those who have undergone amputation for gangrenous changes of limb. 24 patients (12%) died in their postoperative period and a higher rate of mortality was seen in Complex Major Surgery (44.4%, 4% of all) and emergency surgery (17.5%). These patients had multiple comorbidities. The rate of mortality (= Clavien V) in a similar study by M. Bolliger et al [5] was 10.3% overall. Mentula et al [14] conducted a similar study in which the mortality rate was 18.2% after emergency surgery which is almost similar.

Despite validation of Clavien- Dindo score, the Clavien system has considerable drawbacks that limit its readability and interpretation. For example, because each grade must be taken into account independently in the absence of a summative interpretation, the fact that it is given as ordinal data restricts its capacity to thoroughly evaluate two treatment alternatives (such as open vs. laparoscopic surgery). Additionally, cross-grade comparison is limited in the absence of a weighting mechanism (e.g., three Grade-I issues vs. one Grade-III complication cannot be compared). Several studies have shown that Comprehensive Complication Index (CCI) was superior to the Clavien-Dindo classification system [17-19].

Limitations of the Study

Small sample size and limited period of study. The complication can be due to comorbidities than the surgery itself which were not considered in this study. The study was carried out in a single centre but it would be more representative if the study would have been done at multicentre and at different geographical locations. The subjects also tended to present with more comorbidities than would be the case in a smaller center with more elective surgery. We attempted to depict the complexity of the operations by using the accounting system of the BUPA Score, which may not be the most precise measurement, although it gave us a reasonable approach to differentiate.

Conclusion

The Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications can be used in both elective and emergency surgery patients. BUPA Score is a simple and easier method to classify complexity of surgery and we can easily correlate the complexity of surgery and complications with the Clavien Dindo Classification. For risk adjustment, patients' comorbidities, preoperative organ dysfunctions and the type of surgery should be included in the database of surgical complications.

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